

The New Paradigm of Mass Communication

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Abstract

The emergence of the manufacture of dissent model on the Internet is a consequence of deep changes in the global communication system and of a failure to grasp the new principles that structure it. In the twenty-first century, these changes are marked by a relocation of centres of power and by the transformation of the hierarchical architecture through which information is disseminated. The classical paradigm of communication, based on the transfer and filtering of data from a single centre to multiple endpoints, no longer reflects the reality of digital media. The delay in recognising and theorising these new trends in global communication contributes to dysfunction in national systems and intensifies tensions and disagreements within states. The growing mismatch between the inherited communication paradigm and the networked reality of the Internet is therefore one of the underlying causes of contemporary crises in democratic societies.

Keywords: manufacture of dissent; new paradigm of communication; Denis McQuail

The old paradigm is declining

In 2013 Denis McQuail published his article “Reflections on Paradigm Change in Communication Theory and Research”, addressing long-standing concerns about the absence of a general theory of communication. He notes the unease surrounding the close ties between communication research, political power and commercial interests, and the awareness that much empirical work is commissioned or custom-made. The lack of a shared theoretical framework, common principles and a clear path of development is evident. McQuail asks what a paradigm shift would actually mean: why it is needed, what would be gained from it, and whether change is sometimes pursued as an end in itself. At first glance the existing system appears stable. Media industries stimulate conspicuous consumption of trivial and sensational news; political actors use communication to form opinions and beliefs on a global scale; audiences receive continuous entertainment and seem broadly satisfied; and communication science is flourishing if measured by the volume of publications. None of the main participants in the mass communication process appears particularly interested in abandoning the traditional paradigm. Yet, McQuail argues, change is already taking place, even if it has not yet been adequately described in new theories or concepts. Internet media technologies have generated a new perception of communication as a much broader and more complex social phenomenon. The main twentieth-century paradigm is therefore in gradual decline and, as it erodes, a new paradigm emerges. The old paradigm was shaped by the discovery of the immense power of advertisers and propagandists and their capacity to reach, more or less simultaneously, almost the entire population. Within this framework, the audience is conceived as a scattered but

essentially homogeneous crowd in which individuals can be unified through exposure to the same messages. Because the audience is treated as uniform, it is assumed that messages can be universal. Communication is imagined as making direct contact with each person while bypassing local culture, ideology, customs, family, religion and politics. Centralised control of content at the source is taken for granted, and the effects of communication are expected to be easily predictable, producing the conformity desired by the state or other power elites. Understanding communication primarily as an efficient technical transfer of information from one point to another now appears outdated.

The new paradigm

In contemporary conditions, computer networks are used above all to form new human communities. The Internet functions primarily as an information and interaction space inhabited by digital avatars. Online communication is characterised by group interaction and by the division of individuals into communities based on shared views, interests and identities. The transport of information is no longer an end in itself but serves the deeper purpose of uniting those who circulate and interpret it. Such group formation almost inevitably implies conflict and disagreement with other groups. Under these conditions, a universal communication model based solely on transmission cannot be sustained. The effects of communication are not limited to the movement of data; they include the continual reorganisation and transformation of human communities. For decades, communication studies focused on the technical aspects of transmission and on the use of media for control. Rather than seeking a complete replacement for this model, an alternative perspective can be developed alongside it, precisely in those areas where communication theory has the least experience. In the traditional understanding of mass communication, media became powerful instruments of social management and control when they were meant to act as intermediaries. For McQuail, this propaganda model of media power is marked by voluntary, often enthusiastic public compliance. In democracies, the persuasive suggestions of mass media are not imposed openly, as in totalitarian regimes; it is crucial that individuals continue to feel their choices are personal and free. Instead of issuing direct commands, media messages create needs, desires and inclinations within isolated members of the mass. Since the early twentieth century, fascination and anxiety have surrounded the power of advertising, public relations and propaganda, fuelled by rapid advances in communication technology. In this conceptual universe, changes in attitudes and behaviour are assumed to depend primarily on the content transmitted and received. Media messages assault traditional culture, overwhelm its filters, regulations and norms, and become key instruments of power, with almost instantaneous influence over minds. Individuals are subsumed under the logic of the mass and are treated as material to be shaped by media in the service of state and corporate elites.

The new media effects

The study of media effects has therefore become a central focus of communication research in the twenty-first century, and earlier theories are undergoing revision. McQuail directs attention away from declared motives or intended outcomes and towards the concrete consequences for particular communities and individuals. The audience is no longer treated as an undifferentiated mass; the complex pattern of media effects is increasingly recognised. Yet the idea of the omnipotence of mass media continues to reappear as a reassuring mechanism in times of unrest and social conflict. Theories of media hegemony confront accounts of expanding civic

consciousness and of critical voices in journalism and popular culture. These approaches became influential among students and researchers in the 1970s and 1980s, revealing how little substance there is in the classical doctrine of journalistic objectivity. In reality, the logic of media and the possibility of manipulation routinely take precedence over truth and Enlightenment ideals. Theories of cultivation, agenda-setting and the spiral of silence drew a new picture in which mass media function as an organised system for manufacturing consent, enabling manipulation and social control. In democracies, such control is never absolute and depends fundamentally on the audience. Research on media effects therefore shifted to examining the complexity of influence on different individuals and social groups. The Internet made it possible to know audiences in far greater detail as sets of individuals whose behaviour can be tracked and recorded. This knowledge, in turn, enabled more sophisticated mechanisms of manipulation. At the same time, the free circulation of information in social networks revived the ritual view of communication as the creation of human communities. Strong communities can exist independently of media and are built through direct human contact; for them, media are merely spaces for exchanging information. Today the Internet has taken the place of a shared public square, functioning as an open market of ideas and opinions. This open communicative environment complements the hypothesis of powerful media with a broader constructivist perspective. From this standpoint, news agencies and other media organisations produce coverage under external pressure and constraints, and the resulting messages are interpreted differently according to the perceptions and interests of various audiences. The concept of media effects expands to include multiple types of influence and to require new methods of research.

The new audiences

The older image of the audience as a homogeneous mass nevertheless remains attractive because it suits the needs of advertising and propaganda. Increasingly, however, people are thought of as active, self-determining and interpretive beings. It is impossible to predict all the consequences of mass communication, but trends can still be identified. The systematic collection and digital storage of data on individual behaviour has contributed to this new view. Audiences are now constantly monitored online and appear as active, shifting and composite ensembles. In earlier periods, the lack of technology for such monitoring meant that audiences could only be imagined according to the needs of media and survey research. If the audience is conceived as an undifferentiated mass, the appropriate strategy is to manufacture consent through coordinated propaganda campaigns. If it is conceived as a community of independent interpreters, the strategy of choice becomes divide and rule: splitting the audience into warring groups as a way of mastering the whole. This latter model finds ideal conditions for development on the Internet. The way in which elites conceive of the audience is thus not merely a technical issue; it is an ethical and political problem central to democratic media research. When power elites in democracies do not trust or respect individuals, they treat them as consumers rather than citizens, and the very meaning of democracy is emptied. Businesses and private corporations then appear better equipped to satisfy consumer needs, while trust in the wisdom of public opinion – on which democracy depends – erodes. Contemporary media research attempts to acknowledge that trust and moves beyond the notion of a mass audience. New terms such as “consulting” and “conversational” audiences are proposed, but the older image of the anonymous, manipulable audience remains deeply entrenched and practically useful for media designers, advertisers, marketing experts, influencers and information merchants. In this context, Roland Burkart’s concept of the “dispersive audience” becomes

important. In his book *Kommunikationswissenschaft* (1998), he describes audiences that share certain opinions and interests but do not form genuine communities. Such dispersive audiences generate “non-public opinion”: an aggregate of similar views without the dense social ties that characterise public spheres. These audiences consist of individuals connected only by their interest in particular media messages. Instead of stable human communities, they produce networks whose unity resembles the behaviour of flocks or swarms more than the deliberative consent of a human society. They are not long-term social formations but arise ad hoc. There are no direct interpersonal relationships between members; recipients are anonymous and only know that many others are exposed to the same content. Burkart therefore questions whether genuine communication is even possible under these conditions, since communication presupposes reciprocity and community-building. Mass communication risks becoming a myth: a continuous flow of publication and commentary in which real personal contact no longer occurs. Communicative acts become automatic, ritualised habits. The question of media effects, in this context, has no single answer. Constant change demands constant innovation in methods and approaches. For Burkart, the effects of mass media resemble a bottomless barrel. The underlying problems of mass communication can only be grasped through the study of groups and communities, since these reveal the social nature of individuals. The Internet and social networks provide a unique opportunity to explore this nature and the persistent drive to form groups of all kinds. Although the Internet is a new medium, it incorporates older mass media within itself, and therefore all theories and hypotheses of mass communication must be tested under online conditions.

The new research

The emergence of dispersive audiences and non-public opinion is closely linked to the disintegration of the large family and to the erosion of intimate, spontaneous face-to-face communication. As society becomes more complex, organisational demands increase at the expense of personal contact. Non-public opinion thus becomes a mere sum of similar attitudes among isolated individuals and does not amount to a community. In processes of industrialisation and democratisation, “primary groups” such as family, friendship circles, neighbourhoods and local communities have continued to provide external social stabilisation. These groups are intimate, direct, personal and emotional. Treating large populations as a mass or crowd simplified communication research for decades, but modern technologies now make it possible to create detailed maps of human relations, of group memberships and communal attachments. Internet audiences are not simply masses of atomised individuals; they are subdivided into interconnected small groups whose internal relations matter as much as media messages. For Burkart, the analysis of these networks of groups and connections is essential for understanding the new paradigm of public opinion formation. In people’s political decisions, interpersonal communication increasingly outweighs the direct influence of media. The growing influence of groups and opinion leaders online has contributed to the decline of the traditional power of mass media. Public trust in established media diminishes, while charismatic leaders gain followers. Mass media turn out to be more effective in reinforcing existing views than in changing minds, and often exert little or no influence. This failure has become a key topic in media research. Burkart therefore insists that the central question is what people actually do with media: how they use media content, how they incorporate it into their lives, and how it interacts with social and cultural factors. The impact of mass media depends not simply on exposure to messages but on the use and interpretation of information. As a result, research has shifted away from purely mechanistic and mathematical models, which are easy

to manipulate and to present as media events, and which often serve the interests of influencers and would-be persuaders. Such models tend to ignore beliefs, values, personal experience, philosophies of life, loyalties, movements and the complex patterns of communication and debate that shape public life. Although empirical research cannot capture all these dimensions, a more optimistic view of the new communication paradigm sees contemporary communication as more open, organic and generative of ideas. With connectivity and feedback, each participant is both author and audience, and manipulation, though still possible, is often voluntarily accepted as part of group belonging and loyalty. In this spiral of continuous sharing and commenting, the classic notion of “mass media effects” becomes less useful. New digital technologies allow comprehensive monitoring and measurement of communication processes, but they also require greater attention to detail and relationships. The aim is not simply to confirm pre-existing theories but to understand and, where possible, support natural processes of community formation and dissolution. Only when the disintegration of older systems of public communication is properly analysed can new and better systems be developed. The inertia of the old mass communication model continues to fuel the manufacture of dissent, with all its negative effects. Unfortunately, the new technological possibilities for monitoring human behaviour are mainly exploited by private and corporate interests and by biased, commissioned research that multiplies annually. Businesses have traditionally adapted more quickly than state and public institutions to the new paradigm and have drawn profit from shifting patterns of demand. Public authorities lag behind in using communication technologies, even as they try to build systems of e-government. E-government is not just a technical innovation; it is a project for a new social contract in which machines participate in producing consent and social order. For some, algorithms represent the last hope for addressing disinformation, conflict propaganda, fake news and systematic distortion. Yet McQuail doubts that a paradigm shift will be easy. The old models still work well for many influential actors in advertising and media, who will exploit them to the limit. Audiences themselves do not appear to demand radical change.

The question, then, is who needs the new paradigm. McQuail places the responsibility on communication researchers, who must sense the dynamics of change and follow them in their work. Every significant scientific idea acquires value because it responds to the spirit of its time. Each era generates its own concepts and world. In the history of science, the most recent discoveries are often prefigured in the oldest theories; the true innovator is the one who can build a bridge across time. Technological change alone is insufficient to transform a paradigm, but “directions for the development of a new and broader understanding of communication are noted and are still piling up”. Communication theory must adjust to changes in its object, and this adjustment demands a paradigm shift. If the trends traced in this book are correct, communication understood merely as information transfer must give way to an understanding of communication as a ritual for creating and maintaining communities. The manufacture of dissent threatens precisely those forms of understanding characteristic of traditional human communities. A new paradigm for studying communication must therefore also focus on this organised division of people. Wide access to information and research on the Internet enables anyone to study communication and its effects. Equality and communication among researchers are crucial for change. The paradigm of domination and power in communication must be overcome, and the long-discussed idea of a new information order, made technically possible by the Internet, becomes a central task.

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